

THEORY OF THE VERB IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. This article is devoted to theory of the verb which gives general definitions of "verb" by scholars. In addition, it provides information about linguistic and specific features of the verb, as well as, it discusses types of the verb.

Keywords: semantic, function, meaning, form, grammatical meaning, class, objects.

ТЕОРИЯ ГЛАГОЛА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена теории глагола, в которой даны общие определения ученых о «глаголе». Кроме того, в нем дается информация о языковых и видовых особенностях глагола, а также обсуждаются виды глагола.

Ключевые слова: семантика, функция, значение, форма, грамматическое значение, класс, объекты.

INTRODUCTION

Yu.S. Maslov defines a verb as a group of words expressing the grammatical meaning of an action, that is, a dynamic sign representing tenses. The grammatical meaning of the action can be interpreted broadly: it is not only a literal concept, but it can simply be said that what a certain object is, belongs to a certain person or class of objects:

A chair is a piece of furniture. He wrote a letter. He will soon recover. The important thing is that the verb does not express the character of permanence in relation to a person or object, but necessarily a sign of relation to some time interval (or unlimited time). This sign is another name for action, or the personal (Finite) forms of the verb always represent an action related to an agent (owner), so the syntactic function of the personal forms of the verb is always the same: they always act as participles in the sentence.

REVIEW

The inflectional system of verbs is richer and more diverse than other word groups. It includes not only the syntactic method but also the analytical form in inflectional languages. It should be said that the verb is the only word group with an analytic form. For the reasons given above, it is not justified to use the nouns used together with the article with the adjectives 'more', 'most' as in analytical forms. [1, 47].

On the other hand, the word-forming structure of the verb is, one might say, not rich. A small number of suffixes, verbs formed by conversion, as well as verbs formed by reversion (N.N. Asomova's term), that is, the formation of verbs by dropping the last part of nouns:

- to blackmail (*blackmailing* сўзидан)
- to sebathe (*seabathing* сўзидан)

Common suffixes of the verb include suffixes from Germanic languages: -en: to redden, to strengthen; suffix originating from Romance languages: -fy: to magnify, to dignify; also -ize: to fraternize, to mobilize can be an example.

All English verbs are divided into two groups based on morphological features, namely, past tense and adjective form 2. A large group consists of standard verbs, which are formed by adding the suffix '-ed', which has three different phonetic variants, depending on the last sound of the stem. For example, the suffix '-ed' forming the past tense has the sound [d] after a voiced consonant or vowel - saved [seivd], echoed [ikoud]; produces the [t] sound after a voiceless consonant - looked [lukt], and the [id] sound after a dental sound: loaded [loudid]. In terms of form, this suffix has only one form: '-ed'.

The second group consists of non-standard verbs, which in turn are divided into several groups. They are formed by changing the vowel in the stem, sometimes adding a suffix to the end of the stem. This is an unproductive method, and the new verbs that appear in Middle English and later are of the standard type, with a few exceptions of course. But the non-standard group is stable, even if some non-standard verbs have become standard.

Intransitive verbs form a special group: to put, to let, to hit, to cast.

The so-called mixed group includes verbs that are formed by changing the vowel in the stem and adding a suffix:

- to keep- kept- kept
 - to weep- wept- wept
- 'to be' the verb to be has formed its own forms:
- am-is-are; was-were

DISCUSSION

Functional classification of verbs refers to the ability of a verb to appear in one or another participle. This feature comes from the level of direct lexical meaning of the verb. Independent verbs are verbs that have a strong lexical meaning and express an independent action or state. There are also auxiliary and modal verbs. Auxiliary verbs participate in the analytical form of the verb as a complete grammatical component. They completely lose their lexical meaning, so they can be used together with independent verbs that are completely incompatible in terms of lexical meaning: in the example of 'I have lost my umbrella', the verb 'to lose' should not be used together with 'have'. Loss of exactly lexical semantics of auxiliary verbs is the main sign of analytic form, i.e. lack of syntactic connection between the components of the form. [2, 48]

The second group of auxiliary verbs are linking verbs. Their grammatical function, according to A.I. Smirnitsky, is reflected in the connection of the subject (or event) with any sign. Consequently, the linking verb serves as an independent syntactic unit. In addition, linking verbs are used to some extent preserving their lexical semantics, the lexical meaning is reflected in the character it connects. The verbs 'to be' and 'to keep' are used to maintain the sign, and the verbs 'to become', 'to get' and 'to turn' are used to change it. [3, 135].

Modal verbs express the attitude of the owner to the action. This relationship is probability, obligation, etc. is their grammatical meaning. It remains unclear whether these can be called lexical meanings. It is possible that grammatical and lexical semantics are harmonizing in the attitude expressed by them here.

The paradigm of modal verbs is not perfect. They completely lack the category of person and number, which is rudimentarily reflected in full-meaning verbs. Also, not all of them have past tense forms. Since there are no future tense forms, the meaning is conveyed through figurative turns.

Auxiliary and modal verbs can also be substitute verbs or representatives: ‘You are now supposed to be telling something that is grief to you, are you not?’ (Th.D.)

‘And I still say that the sensible thing is for me to go and talk to him, since you won’t’ (Wilson)

The general grammatical meaning of the verb is to express action and state as a process. State expression is characteristic of other word groups. However, in the verb it is expressed in the way of transition from one state to another. In all languages, the verb is one of the independent word groups, and it is one of the problematic issues studied by linguists. The famous linguist V. V. Vinogradov calls this word group a complex and voluminous word group, while A. I. Smirnitsky considers verbs to be a complex word group. M.Bloch, A.S.Barkhudarov, B.A.Ilish, I.I.Ivanova, B.A.Khaymovich and B.I.Rogovskaya also confirm that the word group of verbs is a complicated and comprehensive word group. The verb has a complex nature, because, on the one hand, its grammatical categories, and on the other hand, its types with different lexical and grammatical properties are the reason why it is called complex. Linguists give different definitions of the verb. For example, Jigadlo considers a verb to be a group of words that names an action and expresses a state. [4, 165]

A.S. Barkhudarov believes that a verb is a group of words with grammatical categories such as voice, aspect, tense, and person. M. Bloch admits that the verb is a group of words indicating general categories, the meaning of the process, the time of development. [5, 247] B.A. Khaymovich and B.I. The Rogovskayas believe that a verb is a group of words characterized by a lexical-grammatical meaning that represents an action, a process. Professor of our university, G.M. considers it a group of words with expressive lexical-grammatical meaning and morphologically defines verbs as standard (regular) and non-standard 12 (irregular), invariable, mixed (mixed), personal and impersonal (finite and non-finite). [6, 15]

RESULTS

According to their function, English verbs are divided into independent (notional), (functional) auxiliary and auxiliary, and modal verbs. But B.A. Khaimovich and B.I. The Rogovskayas express the opinion that there are no auxiliary and auxiliary verbs, but they are multifunctional (seminotional). They propose to call link verbs independent link (notional link). Verbs are divided into possessive and complementary (subjective and objective) verbs according to their function in the sentence. Possessive (subjective) verbs are related to the noun representing the doer of the action. Complementary (objective) verbs come into contact with words in the role of complement. Verbs in English are divided into terminative and non-terminative verbs according to their meaning:

1. non-terminative - to sleep, to think, to love, to carry.
2. terminative - to hit, to slap, to break.

According to their structure, verbs are divided into the following groups:

1. Simple - sit, walk, work, study, talk, play.
2. Derivative - pacify, intensify, gasify, activate, darken, blacken, rewrite, mistake, subdivide.
3. Composite - whitewash, overlap, outfight, outdoor, to sit up, to give in, to keep on, to insist on.

Verbs in the modern English language, like all independent word groups, can perform a specific task in a sentence. For example they are:

1. Predicate: She plays tennis well.

He works in the garden.

She likes to read books.

Ann is cooking a cake in the kitchen.

Helen knows English well, but she speaks French too.

He lives in London.

2. Subject: To live is to fight. Smoking is a bad habit. [6,187]

3. Object: I remember having seen before. [6,187]

4. Attribute: Here is a book for you to read. (suhbatdan)

5. Adverbial modifier: I came to speak to you. Having done the work, we came back.

He excused her for coming, later she stopped there, as if knowing the secret.

He spoke stammering.

A group of words characterizing an action or situation as a process and having tense, aspect, inclination, proportion, perfect and other grammatical categories is called a verb. The verb mainly shows the activity of a person. For example:

Young Mako and Lanny Swarts are coming here tonight (P. Abrahams)

She gave the bedclothes such a twitch that both her feet became uncovered and she had to creep up the pillows to get them well under again (K. Mansfield).

They sat down, very shaky, and looked at each other.

The words highlighted in these examples are part of the verb group, and they show the activity of the subject in the sentence. Verb forms are divided into definite (finite forms) or predicative form and indefinite (non-finite form) or non-predicative form, depending on whether they are accented or not accented in the sentence. Verb forms that change in the categories of person, number, tense, and mood, and act as participles in a sentence, are called concrete or predicative forms of the verb:

Mrs. Conroy laughed (J. Joyce).

The two young gentlemen asked the ladies ill they might have the pleasure, and Mary Jane turned to Miss Daly (Ibid).

He avoided her eyes he had seen a sour expression on her face (Ibid).

In the above examples, the verbs to laugh-kulmoq, to ask-so'ramoq, to turn-burilmoq, to avoid-voz kechmoq, and to see-ko'rmoq, appear-paydo bo'lmoq in the definite or predicative form.

Forms of verbs that show the action or state in general and show a partial character or subjectivity are called indefinite or non-predicative forms of verbs. Indefinite forms of the verb can indicate an action or state by itself, not in connection with the owner of the sentence, but separated from it. Indefinite forms of the verb usually do not directly indicate categories such as person, number, tense, mood [10,54].

These forms include infinitiv (infinitive), sifatdosh (participle), gerundi (gerund) in Modern linguistics.

The girl, seeing that he had gained the stairs called out after him (J. Joyce).

She had preceded him into the pantry to help him off with his overcoat (Ibid).

Her hair drawn low over the tops of her ears, was grey (Ibid).

He waited outside the drawing-room door until the waltz should finish, listening to the skirts that swept against it and to the shuffling of feet.

He was still discomposed by the girls bitter and sudden retort.

It had east a gloom over him which he tried to dispel by arranging his cuffs and the bows of his tie (Ibid).

Exact forms of verbs act as a participle in a sentence, and indefinite forms can act as a part of a sentence rather than a participle. Infinitive and infinitive verbs have infinitive, past indicative and adjective II forms.

For example: to write – yozmoq, wrote - yozdi (-m, - ng, -k, -ngiz, -lar,) written - yozilgan;

be - bo'lmoq, was - bo'ldi (-m, -ng), were - bo'ldi (-k, -ngiz),
been - bo'lgan.

The second and third forms of many verbs do not differ from each other according to their graphic representation:

to work – o'qimoq, worked - ishladi (-m, -ng, -k, -ngiz, -lar) - worked ishlangan;

to read - o'qimoq, read [red] o'qidi (-m, -ng, -k, -ngiz, -lar), read red) o'qigan, o'qilgan and others.

CONCLUSION

Verbs are divided into two large groups, called correct and incorrect verbs, according to how the past tense forms are formed. Correct verbs. Verbs formed using the suffix -ed in the past tense and the II adjective form are called regular verbs. Incorrect verbs. Verbs formed in the past tense and the second participle without the suffix -ed are called irregular verbs. Irregular verbs are divided into three groups according to their formation:

1) verbs whose stem vowel changes. a) The II adjective form is made using -en: to write - wrote - written to shake - shook - shaken to rise - rose - risen b) No special suffix is added to the II adjective form: to sink - sank - sunk to run - ran - run to do - did - done c) the vowel in the root and the consonant at the end change: to tell - told - told to buy - bought - bought to catch - caught - caught g) the consonant d at the end becomes the consonant t: to send - sent - sent to spend - spent - spent to lend - lent - lent to build - built - built d) is made by suppletive way from various stems: to be - was, were - been to go - went - gone e) modal (defective) verbs without adjective II form: can - could, shall - should, will - would, may -might [11,76].

2) verbs with all three forms are the same: to set - set - set, to hit - hit - hit, to cast - cast - cast, to hurt- hurt- hurt, to cut - cut - cut, to let - let - let. 3) mixed (mixed) verbs. The past tense form of these verbs can be formed using -ed like regular verbs, and the second adjective form can be formed using -en and sometimes with both -ed and -en suffixes: to show- shown - shown, to saw - sawed - sawn, sawed to rive - rived - rived, riven The range of correct verbs in modern English is expanding more and more. The first reason is that verbs from other languages are formed by adding the suffix -ed like regular verbs. For example: He looked suddenly savage, and Dr. Macphail, getting out of bed, saw that he was heavily tattooed. (W.S. Maugham) [9,268]

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